

Thermodynamic Formation Constants of Metal Chelates of Sulphadiazine Salicylaldimine

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Potentiometric studies have been carried on complexes of Sulphadiazine salicylaldimine (SUDSA) with copper, nickel and cobalt at 25°. The Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti has been applied to determine the protonation constant of the ligand and the formation constants of the complexes. The log k values have been computed by alternative methods. Free energy changes have also been evaluated.

THE synthesis of Sulphadiazine salicylaldimine and conductometric and spectrophotometric study of Sulphadiazine salicylaldimine complexes of copper, nickel and cobalt has been reported earlier^{1,2}. The proton ligand stability constants of ligand and stepwise metal ligand stability constants have been obtained by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration techniques^{3,4} as used by Irving-Rossotti⁵. Free energy values have also been evaluated.

Experimental

Materials

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Metal perchlorates were prepared by dissolving carbonates in perchloric acid. The excess perchloric acid was distilled off. On cooling perchlorates crystallised out and were suction filtered, washed and analysed.

Copper was estimated iodometrically, cobalt was estimated as tetrapyridine cobalt dithionate⁶ and nickel with dimethyl glyoxime.

Sulphadiazine salicylaldimine (SUDSA) was prepared as reported earlier¹.

The solution of SUDSA (0.01M) and salt solutions (0.005 M) were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount in 20% acetone.

The sodium hydroxide (carbon dioxide free) solution was prepared by a standard technique⁶ using Analar material (E. Merck).

Stock solutions of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid were prepared by dissolving Analar (Riedel) $\text{NaClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Analar HClO_4 (E. Merck) in double distilled water.

Solutions of carbon dioxide free sodium hydroxide and 0.025 HClO_4 were standardised potentiometrically by usual procedures.

Procedure

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration against sodium hydroxide of the three mixtures.

Mixture A—Perchloric acid 0.025M
Mixture B—Perchloric acid 0.025M + SUDSA 0.01M
Mixture C—Perchloric acid 0.025M + SUDSA 0.01M + Metal solution 0.005M.

such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. Neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added so as to maintain the ionic strength to 0.02M. The final volume was adjusted to 100 ml using 20% acetone. The titrations were carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere at 25° with the cell immersed in a thermostat bath. The design of the cell was such that it allowed nitrogen to be flushed through and above the solutions it could also accommodate a glass stirrer, a micro burette, a glass electrode and one limb of the agar bridge which was connected to the electrode externally. A pH meter (Beckman model H₂) was used for pH measurement.

The difference in the amount of sodium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations (B & C) is a measure of the extent of complexation.

To calculate the formation constant of the ligand proton system the value of $\bar{n}A$ at different pH values were calculated using the (A) acid, and (B) ligand + acid titration curves. The ligand protonation formation curve was obtained by plotting graph between $\bar{n}A$ values and pH. \bar{n} values were calculated using (B) ligand + acid and (C) metal + ligand + acid titration curves. The metal ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal ligand formation curves drawn between \bar{n} and pL .

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curves which proves that the liberation of protons is due to chelation. Various computational methods⁷ viz., interpolation at half \bar{n} values, least square, and graphical methods were applied to obtain the proton-ligand stability constant and metal-ligand stability constant. The mean values at an ionic strength ($\mu=0.2M$) have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I

Ion	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β	ΔG .
H				Log $\beta^H = 4.9$
Cu(II)	4.51	3.01	7.52	-10.28 Kcals/ Mole
Ni(II)	4.14	2.35	6.49	- 8.87 Kcals/ Mole.
Co(II)	3.55	1.68	5.23	- 7.15 Kcals/ Mole.

The results reveal that Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) form 1 : 2 complexes and the sequence of stability

is found to be $Cu > Ni > Co$ which is in accordance with Irving and Williams⁸.

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